

Present Knowledge of the Chemistry of Proanthocyanidins*

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The chemical nature and origin of the bright red and blue colouring matters of flowers, fruits and leaves have been attracting the attention of scientists from very early times. But it was only during the years 1913-1917 which included the first World War that Willstatter succeeded in the isolation of the main anthocyanins in a pure condition and established their chemical constitution. He showed that anthocyanidins are responsible for the colour of the molecules and they are in combination with sugars forming the anthocyanins. A typical example is cyanin of the red rose, a diglucoside of cyanidin (I). The exact positions of the sugar units were finally established by Robinson by adopting the methods of synthesis. He not only synthesised the anthocyanidins but also accomplished the synthesis of the glycosidic anthocyanins. Cyanin was correctly represented by structure II. Much work has been done subsequently on the possible biosynthesis of these colouring matters and also on their utilization for the study of genetics.

As already mentioned the origin of anthocyanins has been engaging attention for a fairly long time. Many flowers which were first colourless were noted to develop colour rapidly on the plant. Further many living plant materials when subjected to injury quickly developed these colours. Obviously there were some colourless substances which acted as precursors. About the same time as Willstatter's work on anthocyanins, Tswett observed that numerous plant extracts turned red when treated with acids and concluded that the red colouring matters so formed were very similar to natural anthocyanidins. This observation has been confirmed in later years by comparison with synthetic anthocyanidins using paper chromatography. Soon after Tswett, Rosenheim made similar observations with the leaves of the grape vine and fruits of white grapes and considered that they contained colourless substances, glycosidic in nature, which he called leucoanthocyanins. Later it was realised that most of these colourless compounds were free from sugars and hence should be called leucoanthocyanidins. The white grapes that were an early source of leucoanthocyanidin were not however fully studied till recently and the observations made in our laboratory will be mentioned later. The conversion of colourless leuco compounds seems to take place rapidly by the action of the enzymes of plant

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materials and especially under acid conditions as in fruits. Side by side considerable polymerisation of the leucoanthocyanidins takes place to yield substances called phlobaphenes. Later survey by Robinson showed that these leucoanthocyanidins were widely distributed especially in fruit peels and woody parts of plants and they were flavan-3, 4-diols but they were too unstable to be isolated and studied except in specially favourable cases like cyanomacurin and peltogynol. It was only during the past twelve years that this could be done with many of the commonly occurring leucoanthocyanidins. They are present in high concentration in woods, barks and gums; woods are particularly suitable for their extraction in a pure condition.

Many tanning materials are also good sources of leucoanthocyanidins. The compounds are strongly astringent in their properties and have marked effect on animal and plant systems. In earlier days attempts were made to isolate and study monomeric forms though polymers were also largely accompanying them. Recent studies have led to the isolation of more dimers and trimers involving the same flavan-diol (III) or having a catechin (VII) or gallo catechin (VIII) molecule as an end group. Some of the combinations obtained in the course of the study of fruits, woods and barks are discussed below. They undergo in the presence of acids depolymerisation accompanied by oxidation to yield anthocyanidins. In most cases cyanidin is the end product indicating the wide occurrence of leuco-cyanidin unit (III). However, polymers involving leucopelargonidin (IV), leucofisetinidin (V) and leucodelphinidin (VI) are also common. Recently Freudenberg in consultation with Robinson has introduced the term "proanthocyanidins" to include all compounds that yield anthocyanidins on treatment with acids. This is not intended necessarily to imply that they are precursors in anthocyanidin biogenesis. The above compounds will therefore come under polymeric proanthocyanidins. In this lecture I have used the term leucoanthocyanidins for the monomeric flavan-3, 4-diols. Proanthocyanidins seem to play an important part in biological processes but this has not been fully studied. Their presence in foods considerably affects taste, stability towards oxidation and also colour.

For the elucidation of the structure of the polymeric proanthocyanidins special methods are found necessary. The molecule is first degraded into the individual C-15 units and the identification of these made. The common method is acid hydrolysis whereby proanthocyanidins split into parts giving rise to anthocyanidin chlorides (derived from the flavan-3, 4-diol parts) and catechins, if they are present. During hydrolysis acid concentrations should be kept below 6%; higher concentrations normally affect the catechins as well as the anthocyanidins. Anthocyanidin chlorides are identified by comparison with authentic samples using paper chromatography and absorption spectra in the visible region. For example, cyanidin chloride in ethanolic 0.1% HCl has a maximum at 545 m μ and the maximum is shifted to higher wavelength with aluminium chloride. The yields of catechins

are usually low and the method of identification is co-chromatography on paper or T.L.C. using authentic samples. The chromatograms are examined under an U. V. lamp after exposing to ammonia when they show fluorescent spots. When sprayed with alcoholic ferric chloride they give characteristic coloured spots.

The next step is the determination of the molecular size by mass spectral analysis. In this study the molecule splits into the individual O-15 units indicating the labile nature of the linkages between them. The proanthocyanidins themselves are unsuitable for this purpose. Their methyl ethers (IXa) are more suitable. They can be prepared by the action of diazomethane on their methanolic solutions; if the methylation is not complete it is completed using dimethyl sulphate, potassium carbonate and acetone. In some cases the latter methylating agent is used directly. In these processes only phenolic groups are methylated. The remaining alcoholic groups can be later acetylated by means of acetic anhydride and pyridine in the cold. The methyl ether acetates (IXb) are quite stable and most suitable for study. On the other hand direct acetylation of the proanthocyanidins yields acetates (IXc) in which all the hydroxyl groups are acetylated. Frequently the estimation of the number of acetoxy groups provides a good guide. These groups are also removed by boiling with acids and the pure acetates give the anthocyanidins just like the original hydroxy compounds. The methyl ether acetates on acid hydrolysis yield the methylated anthocyanidins (Ib). These transformations are summarised in the following chart using monomeric procyanidin or leucocyanidin.

Later periodate oxidation is used; the methyl ether in methanol is treated with a known amount of sodium metaperiodate and the amount of periodate consumed is quantitatively determined by iodimetry. This is particularly useful for finding out the presence or absence of the diol system and in case a diol system is present, the molecular size of the proanthocyanidin could be calculated because one mole of periodic acid is consumed by a diol unit. Rast method even though useful for the determination of the molecular weight has limitations. I.R. spectra are not particularly useful for the structural study of condensed proanthocyanidins since most of them give similar spectra and resemble in general hydroxy flavonoids. However the absence of the C=O frequency in the spectra of the proanthocyanidins or their methyl ethers could be used for indicating this group; with the acetates of the proanthocyanidins two sharp bands (or a broad band) appear since the C=O frequencies of the acetates of phenolic hydroxyls and alcoholic hydroxyls differ. But N.M.R. spectra are more specific and are useful for the structural elucidation of the proanthocyanidins.

The polymeric proanthocyanidins can be classified into three categories depending

on the mode of linkages between the C-15 units involved. In general fruits do not yield monomeric diols though they contain free catechins. Dimers and higher polymers are found.

(1) *Proanthocyanidins having a -C-O-C- linkage*: These compounds are more readily hydrolysed by dilute acids. In the cases so far described the fission products are found to be cyanidin and catechin or epicatechin.

The first dimeric proanthocyanidin was isolated by Forsyth and Roberts from fresh cacao beans. It gave on mild acid treatment cyanidin chloride and epicatechin. Later, a proanthocyanidin obtained by Freudenberg and Weinges from hawthorn berries (*Crataegus oxyacantha*) was found to be identical in chromatographic behaviour and degradative studies with that of the cacao beans. From the number of hydroxyl groups that can be methylated using diazomethane, and in addition from the number that can be acetylated the product is considered to be a derivative of the 2, 3, 4-triol type, whose 2-hydroxyl group is etherified with the 3-hydroxyl of epicatechin (X). The hawthorn berries contain also a second proanthocyanidin which yields on acid hydrolysis epicatechin and an anthocyanidin which is probably delphinidin.

From the leaves of hawthorn, a proanthocyanidin has been isolated, which differed from the above compounds in being made up of two leucocyanidin units and at the same time lacking a free glycollic system (the methyl ether did not consume periodate). Based on these results structure (XI) has been proposed; in it the two leucocyanidin units are linked through a -C-O-C- linkage involving the hydroxyls at the 4-position of both the units. However, other alternative possibilities can be O-linkage between 3 and 4 and 3 and 3 positions. A proanthocyanidin (XII) which gives rise to (+) catechin and cyanidin on acid hydrolysis has been isolated from the fruits of *Gleditsia triacanthos*; whether this exists in keto or enol form is not clear.

(2) *Proanthocyanidins having a -C-C-linkage*: A more common method of dimerisation involves C-C linkage and the compounds are comparatively more stable to hydrolysis. Essentially they arise from a flavan-3, 4-diol system in which the 4-hydroxyl is highly

reactive and a catechin or another flavan-3, 4-diol with reactive nuclear positions. The linking is considered to be between C₄ and C₃ or C₈. The mechanism of the process can be represented as given below:

What appears to be the same proanthocyanidin was isolated from two sources. (1) Gelman and Dittmar obtained it from the seeds of avocado pear; on acid hydrolysis it yielded cyanidin chloride and a mixture of catechin and epicatechin which was attributed to epimerization at C-3 during acid hydrolysis. N.M.R. spectra of the acetate and the methyl ether supported C(4)—C(8) linked dimeric structure. Freudenberg and Weinges isolated it from colanuts. Mass spectral study of the methyl ether acetate gave confirmatory evidence for structure (XIII). The fragmentation pattern is represented below:

About the same time in our laboratories was isolated a proanthocyanidin from the stem-bark of *Myrica nagi*. On acid hydrolysis it gave delphinidin chloride and catechin. The methyl ether did not consume periodate. In the mass spectrum of the proanthocyanidin methyl ether there were peaks above 400 mass units indicating it to be a dimer. These are closely similar to the mass spectral data of Freudenberg and Weinges except that with our compound since a leucodelphinidin unit is involved, the peaks are 30 mass units higher. Structure (XIV) has been proposed for it and has been confirmed by N.M.R. spectrum.

A proanthocyanidin has recently been isolated from the stem bark of *Rhododendron grande* in our laboratories by Rangaswami and Venkateswarlu. This differed from the earlier ones in that it gave only cyanidin chloride on acid hydrolysis and no catechin or epicatechin could be identified. Periodate oxidation of the methyl ether indicated it to be a dimer with a free diol grouping. Based on the analytical and spectral data, structure (XV) has been proposed. The proanthocyanidins recently obtained by Roux and coworkers from *Acacia mearnsii* form an interesting group. The heartwood gave bileucofisetinidin (XVI) and its absolute configuration and the mode of linkage have been determined by the N.M.R. and mass spectral data. This is somewhat exceptional in that the less active nuclear position of a resorcinol part is involved. From the bark of the same plant three proanthocyanidins based on leucofisetinidin and catechin (XVII), leucorobinetinidin and catechin (XVIII) and galloocatechin (XIX) have been isolated in which the nuclear position of the 6,7-dihydroxy system of catechins is involved indicating its greater reactivity than the nuclear positions of the concerned leucoanthocyanidin part.

(3) *Proanthocyanidins having both -C-C- and -C-O-C- linkages*: A proanthocyanidin belonging to this category has been found in *Aesculus hippocastanum*. It gave on hydrolysis cyanidin chloride and catechin. From the analytical and N.M.R. spectral data structure (XX) has been proposed with possible alternatives indicated.

For a long time it has been known that catechins polymerise in the presence of acids. In this process the oxide ring opens and linking takes place between the 2 and 8 or 6-positions, and polymers of different degrees arise. The flavandiols (leucoanthocyanidins) are much faster in acid catalysed polymerisation being 200-300 times as fast and this is attributed to the presence of the benzylic-4-hydroxyl group and the linking seems to take place largely with the nuclear position 8 or 6 of another molecule. Therefore in their case the conditions most favourable for polymerisation are two: (1) the activity of 4-hydroxyl and (2) the activity of the nuclear positions 6 and 8. The former being benzylic in nature enters into reactions very fast under mildly acid conditions. If this is engaged in internal ring formation as in cyanomaclurin (XXI) there is considerable stability and there is similarity with catechins. In regard to the nuclear positions a 5,7-dihydroxy system as in leucocyanidin is most suitable for reactivity and polymerisation takes place very readily. If the 5-position is unsubstituted then the compounds are far more stable though they may also eventually enter into combination. This feature explains the readiness with which the mollisacaidin (XXII) group and peltogynol (XXIII) are isolated and preserved.

After the initial C-C linking has been established in the polymerisation, dehydration to yield -C-O-C- linkage may take place. Other modes are also possible and are found in the type of polymers mentioned in the preceding paras.

During our study of deciduous fruits high polymers of proanthocyanidins are met with. As was earlier stated white grape skins and seeds were the earliest to be studied by Rosenheim; however, the nature of the compounds was not fully understood. In our laboratories, we have made an investigation of the proanthocyanidins of the seeds and the skins of white grapes. Ethyl acetate soluble portions of grape seeds and skins contain negligible amount of the proanthocyanidin. From the seeds an ethylacetate insoluble proanthocyanidin has been isolated which on acid hydrolysis gave only cyanidin chloride and no catechin or epicatechin could be detected. The methyl ether did not consume periodate indicating the absence of a free glycolic grouping. Based on the molecular weight determination, methoxyl and acetoxy estimation and analytical data, it could be formulated as a trimer of leucocyanidin (XXIV). The N.M.R. spectrum also supports this structure.

The methanolic extract of the skins also gave a compound forming only cyanidin chloride on acid hydrolysis. However, it differed in that the methyl ether consumed three moles of periodate per mole of the compound leading to the conclusion that it is glycosidic in nature, being possibly a monoglucoside of leucocyanidin.

The heartwood of *Cedrella toona* has been found to be rich in proanthocyanidins. Acetone extract of the wood was fractionated into ethyl acetate soluble and ethyl acetate insoluble portions. The proanthocyanidin from the ethyl acetate soluble portion gave only

cyanidin chloride on acid hydrolysis and no catechin or epicatechin could be identified. Periodate oxidation of the proanthocyanidin methyl ether indicated it to be dimer having structure (XXV); this has been confirmed by molecular weight determinations and N.M.R. spectrum. The proanthocyanidin from ethylacetate insoluble part has been found to be a trimer (by molecular wt. determination) which on acid hydrolysis gave cyanidin chloride and catechin. The methyl ether did not consume any periodate indicating the absence of a free glycollic grouping. Based on the analytical data of the proanthocyanidin and its derivatives, molecular weight determinations and N.M.R. spectral study, structure (XXVI) has been proposed.

Three glycosidic substances belonging to the proanthocyanidin group have been recently isolated from the bark of *Bassia butyracea*. They have been named Bassianin a, b, and c and they give the same aglycone, cyanidin chloride on acid hydrolysis and contain the same tetra-saccharide unit (R-O-xylose-O-arabinose-O-rhamnose-O-glucose) but appear to differ in their molecular size. Such glycosidic substances seem to occur more frequently than we expected some years back.

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